

STUDY OF THE EFFECT OF THERMAL TREATMENT OF Mn_4Si_7 AND $CoSi_2$ THIN FILMS USING AN INFRARED LAMP IN A HIGH-TEMPERATURE FURNACE IN INERT GAS ENVIRONMENTS (Ar, Kr, Xe) ON THEIR CRYSTAL STRUCTURE

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This study describes the modification of a high-temperature RTP-100 furnace. This furnace is equipped with a turbomolecular pump capable of achieving a vacuum level down to 10^{-4} Pa. It is designed for heating thin films of Mn_4Si_7 and $CoSi_2$ with a thickness of ≤ 0.7 μm in a vacuum or inert gas atmospheres such as Ar, Kr, and Xe. The heating zone measures 100×100 mm. The new furnace design enables vacuum thermal processing of Mn_4Si_7 and $CoSi_2$ coatings applied to Si, SiO_2/Si , and ZrO_2/Si substrates with diameters up to 60 mm in batch mode. Heating is carried out using infrared (IR) lamps. The development of this tubular high-vacuum furnace design is both scientifically and technologically justified. Key technical specifications of the furnace are as follows: Heating system: 24 IR lamps with a total power of 21 kVA, Power supply: 3×32 A, 230 V, 3-phase, Maximum heating temperature: 1473 K, Maximum heating rate: 150 K/s, Vacuum level: 10^{-4} Pa, Temperature profile: programmable, Control system: microcontroller + touchscreen, Dimensions: $505 \times 504 \times 580$ mm Weight: 70 kg

In the experiments, the maximum heating temperature was set to 873 K, and heating was performed using IR lamps with a total power of 18 kVA. The device is capable of operating both in a vacuum and in inert gas environments. Advantages and challenges of heating in vacuum: Heating Si wafers using IR lamps in a vacuum environment helps prevent the rapid oxidation of metals on the wafer surface. However, under such conditions, the evaporation rate of heater materials increases, which may limit their long-term usability. In designing the heating system, factors such as electrical feedthroughs into vacuum, contact resistance, thermal expansion coefficient, thermal conductivity, radiation capability, and mechanical stability must be taken into account. The resistance alloys commonly used in furnaces (X20H80, X15H60Yu3, X23Yu5A, X27Yu5A) are primarily intended for operation in air environments and are not always optimal for IR-lamp-based vacuum furnaces [17–21].

In this research, the structural and electrophysical properties of Mn_4Si_7 and $CoSi_2$ thin films with a thickness of ≤ 0.7 μm , obtained on Si, SiO_2/Si , and ZrO_2/Si substrates using vacuum-thermal treatment technology with infrared (IR) lamps, were analyzed. The experimental data obtained using a specially developed vacuum installation and IR heater proved that parameters such as vacuum level, heating temperature, crystal size, dislocation density, and lattice deformation significantly affect the coating quality. According to X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis, heating processes in the temperature range of 473–873 K lead to an increase in crystallization degree, a decrease in dislocation density, and an improvement in the stability of the crystal lattice. The increase in crystal size and decrease in lattice deformation in Mn_4Si_7 and $CoSi_2$ coatings enhance

the mobility of charge carriers, which results in improved electrical conductivity and optimization of thermoelectric properties. Based on this, it was proven that the electrophysical properties can be effectively controlled by influencing the microstructural parameters through high-temperature heating.